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Critical Gas-Fired Power Plants in Integrated Natural Gas and Electricity Systems

Ricardo Fernández-Blanco, David Pozo, and Ricardo Bolado-Lavín

Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, Petten, Netherlands

Ricardo.Carramolino@ec.europa.eu, David.Pozo-Camara@ec.europa.eu, Ricardo.Bolado-Lavin@ec.europa.eu

Abstract

The interdependence between gas and electricity plays an important role in ensuring energy security in many regions in the world. In the European Union, there are regulatory frameworks that recognize this interdependency and the concept of critical gas-fired power plants (GFPPs) is introduced. Specifically, the Regulation (EU) No 2017/1938 on security of gas supply states that critical GFPPs may be given priority over certain categories of gas customers during gas supply crises when curtailment of gas is unavoidable. However, despite the significance of this issue, the Regulation does not set up clear rules about the designation of critical GFPPs. Within this context, we propose an optimisation problem for finding critical GFPPs in interconnected gas and electricity systems. The optimisation problem accounts for the gas and power system flow representation as well as links between both systems. We then analyse the main drivers for the identification of critical GFPPs such as the electricity network topology, the impact of the natural gas network, and the effect of fuel switching capabilities in GFPPs. In addition, the proposed model allows for a ranking of critical GFPPs provided that they should be prioritised over special categories of gas customers such as protected customers. The proposed methodology is applied to the IEEE Three-Area Reliability Test System (RTS).

Keywords: Critical gas-fired power plants; Gas-electricity interaction; Security of supply; Regulation (EU) No 2017/1938.

1 Introduction

The increasing gas-electricity interdependency has triggered some regulatory changes in the European Union (EU). Regulation (EU) No 2017/1938 concerning measures to safeguard the security of gas supply (hereinafter referred to as the Regulation) acknowledges such linkage and introduces the concept of critical gas-fired power plants (GFPPs), which can be designated by EU Member States (MSs). According to the Regulation, critical GFPPs could be prioritised over certain categories of gas customers (e.g. protected customers) during gas supply crises when curtailment of gas is unavoidable. Hence, it is necessary to consider both natural gas and electricity networks when it comes to identifying such critical GFPPs. However, the Regulation does not set up clear rules about the designation of such plants, e.g. the time of designation is ambiguous or the methodology guidelines for identifying them are unknown.

The preventive action plans of only seven EU MSs, namely Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, Ireland, Malta, and, to a lesser degree, Poland and Spain, address to some extent the gas-electricity interaction. However, the matter of critical GFPPs is discussed explicitly in three of them: Germany, the Netherlands, and Poland. Germany has regulated the concept of “systemically relevant” GFPPs in Section 13f of its Energy Industry Act¹. Unlike the definition of critical GFPPs in the Regulation, this does not imply by itself that the respective GFPPs should be prioritised over protected customers. The Netherlands lists four criteria to determine if a power plant is considered critical². Finally, Poland is the only country providing a list of critical GFPPs without explicitly mentioning the identification methodology.

The research about the gas-electricity nexus has been growing in the last decade [1, 2]. The recent literature related to the identification of critical assets in coupled gas and electricity systems can be categorised into three groups: (i) graph-theory-based methods [3–7], (ii) hierarchical methods [8–10], and (iii) model-based quantitative assessments [11–14].

⁽¹⁾ The German transmission system operators for electricity can designate GFPPs with a nominal capacity above 50 MW as systemically relevant.

⁽²⁾ The criteria are: (i) share in total generation capacity, (ii) their use to balance the electricity grid, (iii) their black start function, and (iv) their criticality for continued operation of vital infrastructures.

Graph theory, which is used in [7], is deemed a promising tool to assess the vulnerability of interdependent gas and electricity systems under cascading failures. The works relying on hierarchical optimisation [8–10] to address the vulnerability of interconnected systems are characterised by two drawbacks: (i) scalability issues in real-world and large-sized transmission networks due to computation tractability, and (ii) reliance on linear steady-state models. This work falls within the last category, i.e. model-based quantitative assessments [11–14]. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, none of the works has focused explicitly on the identification of critical GFPPs in line with the Regulation.

The main contributions of this work are twofold:

- We propose a mathematical model to identify and rank critical GFPPs in interconnected gas and electricity systems to comply with the Regulation. We model the electricity system by using a unit commitment formulation whereas the natural gas system is formulated by means of a mass-flow steady-state model. Unlike the closely related scientific literature, we explicitly address the issue of critical GFPPs.
- We analyse the main drivers for the identification of critical GFPPs such as the network topology and the effect of fuel switching capabilities.

The paper is outlined as follows: Section 2 presents the proposed model to identify critical GFPPs. Section 3 briefly describes the case study and scenarios, while Section 4 analyses the results for a range of scenarios. Section 5 duly draws some concluding remarks.

2 Proposed modelling approach

2.1 Standard joint power and gas dispatch

We adopt a day-ahead optimisation approach with hourly time steps for modelling a coupled gas and electricity system. The proposed mathematical model follows the standard electricity and gas optimal dispatch with power plant unit commitment restrictions. It can be expressed as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{x}^g, \mathbf{v}} f_{cost}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v}) + f_{cost}^g(\mathbf{x}^g) \quad (1a)$$

subject to:

$$\mathbf{h}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v}) \leq \mathbf{0}, \quad (1b)$$

$$\mathbf{h}^g(\mathbf{x}^g) \leq \mathbf{0}, \quad (1c)$$

$$\mathbf{h}^{e-g}(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{x}^g) \leq \mathbf{0}, \quad (1d)$$

wherein \mathbf{x}^e and \mathbf{x}^g are vectors of continuous dispatching variables associated with the electricity and natural gas systems, respectively; \mathbf{v} is a vector of binary scheduling variables; $f_{cost}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v})$ and $f_{cost}^g(\mathbf{x}^g)$ are the respective cost functions of the electricity and natural gas systems, which include the cost associated with the electricity not-served (ENS) and gas not-served (GNS); $\mathbf{h}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v})$ and $\mathbf{h}^g(\mathbf{x}^g)$ are constrained functions associated with the electricity and natural gas systems; and $\mathbf{h}^{e-g}(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{x}^g)$ is a constrained function representing the coupling between the electricity and natural gas networks [15].

The *electricity system* is modelled as a unit commitment problem driven by the minimization of operation cost $f_{cost}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v})$, while respecting the load-generation nodal balance and generation operational limits. Thus, the set of equations pertaining to the electricity system captures the operational, technical, and economic constraints as represented by (1b). We adopt a DC load flow model for modelling the electricity grid flows and also account for transmission line capacity limits. The generation scheduling constraints model ramp rates, minimum up and down times, start-ups, production limits, and binary scheduling decisions, as in [16].

The *natural gas system* is characterised by a mass-flow steady-state model, driven by the minimization of operation cost $f_{cost}^g(\mathbf{x}^g)$, while respecting operational and technical constraints, as represented by (1c). These constraints include the gas volume nodal balance, pipeline transport, maximum production limits, and other constraints such as gas storage chronological constraints. The interested reader is referred to [15] for an example of a gas system formulation.

The *gas-electricity coupling* is primarily defined by the dependency of the power system on gas. This relationship links the gas offtake for electricity production to the corresponding GFPP and is represented by constraints (1d).

Next, we extend the standard gas-electricity coupling, specifically gas consumption for electricity, by including a new set of equations. These equations capture the fuel-switching capabilities for some GFPPs and the gas-electricity linkage concerning household consumption, alongside the modelling of critical GFPPs.

2.2 Extended formulation for critical GFPP identification

For the identification of critical GFPP, it is important to have a complete representation of the main coupling links between gas and electricity systems. Apart from the gas-for-electricity (1d) connection between both systems, there are another two important linkages that are typically overlooked, or not addressed deeply, in the literature: fuel switching and gas-electricity for critical residential customers.

2.2.1 Fuel switching

A gas-fired generator may be equipped with fuel-switching capabilities and may use the backup fuel in an emergency situation. If the power plant located at bus i has access to backup fuel, the set of equations (2) represents its fuel-switching capabilities. Although fuel switching has no direct coupling with electricity system variables, the gas or alternative fuel availability impact directly to the final way of producing electricity.

$$0 \leq q_{it}^g \leq \bar{q}_{it}^g(1 - w_{it}), \quad \forall i \in I^{FS}, \forall t \in T \quad (2a)$$

$$q_{it}^b w_{it} \leq q_{it}^b \leq \bar{q}_{it}^b w_{it}, \quad \forall i \in I^{FS}, \forall t \in T \quad (2b)$$

$$0 \leq \sum_{t \in T} q_{it}^b \leq \bar{Q}_i^b, \quad \forall i \in I^{FS}. \quad (2c)$$

For modelling fuel-switching (FS) capabilities, we define a binary variable w_{it} in the domain of GFPP that has fuel-switching capabilities, I^{FS} . The variable $w_{it} = 0$ if the GFPP i is using gas in period t , and $w_{it} = 1$ if it is using backup fuel. Thus, the constraint (2a) states that the natural gas offtake of GFPP i , q_{it}^g , is zero if $w_{it} = 1$. However, if $w_{it} = 0$ the GFPP can use any value of volume of gas³ between 0 and \bar{q}_{it}^g . Similarly to constraint (2a), the equation (2b) forces the backup fuel offtake of GFPP i , q_{it}^b to be zero if $w_{it} = 0$. However, if $w_{it} = 1$, the backup fuel offtake is forced to be between a lower and upper limit. Finally, constraint (2c) models the limits of the total available backup fuel for the whole period of study. The backup fuel is typically limited because there are stocks on-site for emergency situations. We also need to modify accordingly gas cost function $f_{cost}^g(x^g)$ to include the binary nature of GFPP with fuel-switching capabilities using the binary variable w_{it} .

2.2.2 Gas-electricity for residential customers

We include constraints for modelling the reliance of the gas residential consumers on electricity. A certain share of households may not be able to use the natural gas in case of a blackout because their gas meters require electricity. To model it, we can include the following constraint linking the electricity and gas residential demand in a specific region:

$$\frac{GNS_{rt}^{resid}}{GD_{rt}^{resid}} \geq \gamma \frac{ENS_{rt}^{resid}}{ED_{rt}^{resid}}, \quad \forall r \in R, \forall t \in T, \quad (3)$$

where R is the set of regions; T is the set of time periods; GNS_{rt}^{resid} and ENS_{rt}^{resid} are the residential GNS and ENS in region r and time period t , respectively; GD_{rt}^{resid} and ED_{rt}^{resid} are the residential gas and electricity demand, respectively; and γ is the factor coupling non-served residential gas and electricity.

Equation (3) imposes a lower bound on the residential gas demand not served, when the electric load shedding is greater than 0, thus linking the gas and electricity demand of residential consumers.

2.2.3 Ranking critical GFPPs

We define the k critical GFPPs as the ones leading to the smallest economic consequences [17]. In other words, the gas and electricity dispatch cost as well as the cost related with the GNS and ENS is minimized while only the k critical GFPPs are supplied. We can model it by solving (1)-(3) and adding specific constraints to select the k -best GFPP (4).

(³) The upper bound limit represent a big-M and not an actual technical limit. It is in general, a value larger than the intake gas capacity that the GFPP i can have from the main gas network.

$$\sum_{i \in I} u_{it} \leq k, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4a)$$

$$v_{it} \leq u_{it}, \quad \forall i \in I^{NFS}, \forall t \in T \quad (4b)$$

$$v_{it} \leq u_{it} + w_{it}, \quad \forall i \in I^{FS}, \forall t \in T \quad (4c)$$

$$0 \leq u_{it} \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall t \in T. \quad (4d)$$

A continuous auxiliary variable⁴ per GFPP i and period t is introduced, u_{it} , (4d). When $u_{it} = 1$, the GFPP i is considered to be critical, otherwise $u_{it} = 0$.

Equation (4a) sets that the total number of GFPPs that can be identified as critical at each time period are at the maximum k , which is a user-defined value. For example, if interested in the single most critical plant, k must be set to 1. Equation (4b) enforces GFPP i to be offline, i.e. $v_{it} = 0$, when the auxiliary variable u_{it} is 0. This equation is defined for the set of GFPP that has no fuel-switching (NFS) capabilities. For the rest of GFPP with switching capabilities, we add (4d) that additionally accounts if the GFPP i is running on natural gas, i.e. $w_{it} = 0$, or backup fuel, i.e. $w_{it} = 1$.

3 Case study

3.1 Data and simulation setup

We apply the proposed model to the updated IEEE Three-Area RTS (hereinafter referred to as RTS-GMLC system) [18]. We have created a stylized gas system comprising only three gas nodes to showcase the proposed methodology. Even though the gas topology is rather small, the main drivers for the identification of critical GFPPs can be adequately discussed.

The electricity network for the RTS-GMLC system is made up of 73 buses and 121 branches in total. The system consists of three regions which are connected by five AC cross-border interconnectors and one DC link. In turn, each region is divided into two zones (e.g. region 3 has zones 31 and 32). The zones 11, 21, and 31 are predominantly consumption areas (lower voltage) whereas most of the production facilities are located in zones 12, 22, and 32 (higher voltage).

There are 10 gas-fired combined cycle (CC) generators with an installed capacity of 355 MW each, and 27 natural gas-fired combustion turbines (CT) generators with an individual installed capacity of 55 MW, which are located among 19 buses. The total capacity amounts to 1095 MW, 1560 MW, 2380 MW, for regions 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The highest installed capacity can be found at bus 323 in region 3⁵.

Finally, we have selected the simulation period 24-30 August of a representative year because the electricity peak demand hour occurs on 26 August at 3 pm. The total electricity demand for that week is 926.8 GWh: 308.8 GWh in region 1, 321.9 GWh in region 2, and 296.2 GWh in region 3. The electricity system is further described in [19].

For the sake of simplicity, we have adopted a three-node gas network⁶ which is made up of three gas nodes, three gas pipelines, and two gas production facilities located at gas nodes 2 and 3, as can be seen in **Figure 1**. In each gas node, there is a “conventional” gas demand that can be itemised by industrial, commercial, and residential consumption. Moreover, the demand for electricity production is linked to the GFPPs of the corresponding region. We also assume that there are neither underground gas storage nor liquefied natural gas facilities.

The production cost of the gas production facilities at nodes 2 and 3 is assumed to be 34.1 and 17.1 \$/MWh, respectively, whereas their maximum production per hour is set to 2.9 and 4.4 GWh. We assume that the available gas volume in the production facilities is unlimited.

There are three pipelines connecting the gas nodes, labelled 2-1, 3-1, and 3-2. The gas flow direction is endogenously defined in the notation, e.g. the gas in pipeline 2-1 flows from gas node 2 to gas node 1. Bidirectional flows are neglected in this illustrative example. We also assume that the maximum amount of gas

(⁴) Note that the equations (4a)-(4c) has integer coefficients and the variables, other than u_{it} , are binary. Thus, u_{it} can take only 0 or 1 values without the need to define it as binary.

(⁵) The technical characteristics of conventional generators (heat rate curve, start and shutdown costs, minimum stable level, and minimum up and down times can be found in <https://github.com/GridMod/RTS-GMLC>.

(⁶) The purpose of the data shown in this example is to showcase the proposed methodology and, under any circumstance, these data should be taken as reference values for real-world gas networks.

that can be stored (linepack) in pipelines 3-1 and 3-2 is 1.5 GWh whereas for pipeline 2-1 it is limited to 0.3 GWh. We set the maximum flow to 1.5 GWh/h. In this gas system, node 3 cannot use any gas from other gas nodes in case of need, which may cause bottlenecks in some cases.

Figure 1. Joint electricity and natural gas network for the RTS-GMLC system.

Source: JRC, 2024.

The simulation period spans from 24 August until 30 August. The conventional gas demand in that period amounts to 174.1 GWh, of which 20% correspond to commercial consumption, 20% to industrial consumption, and 60% to households.

The supply of gas for electricity production and households is prioritised over commercial and industrial customers. Moreover, supply of gas to commercial customers is prioritised over industrial ones.

3.2 Scenarios

We analyse the following scenarios:

- Scenario 0 (SC 0): This scenario represents the results for a reference (SC 0.a) and a congested case (SC 0.b) when the gas network is neglected. In the congested case, cross-border line capacities among the three regions are reduced to half of the original values and the capacity of inter-zonal lines are reduced to 100 MW. The model is made of constraints (1a)-(1b) and (4a)-(4b), (4d).
- Scenarios 1-2 (SC 1-SC 2): These scenarios discuss the results for a reference (SC 1) and a congested case (SC 2), as described in SC 0. These scenarios account for the operation of the natural gas network. We assume a 70% reduction of gas production capacity. In other words, we set the maximum production levels of gas production facilities at gas nodes 2 and 3 to 0.88 and 1.32 GWh, in that order. The core model is (1), (4a)-(4b), (4d). In turn, we consider the following variants:
 - Case 1.a: Reference case and $k = 0$, i.e. there is no gas available for electricity production. Gas is only consumed by conventional consumers.
 - Case 1.b: Reference case and $k = 1$, i.e. only the most critical GFPP is identified each period.
 - Case 1.c: Reference case without including the constraints (4a)-(4b), (4d).
 - Case 2.a: Congested case and $k = 0$.
 - Case 2.b: Congested case and $k = 1$.

- Case 2.c: Congested case without including the constraints (4a)–(4b), (4d).
- Scenarios 3-4 (SC 3–SC 4): Scenarios 1 and 2 account only for the dependence of the electricity system on the natural gas system, so the electricity system does not have any effect on the gas network. For instance, the model in SC 1–SC 2 ignores the fact that some households could not even use the natural gas in the case of an electricity blackout. Therefore, SC 3–SC 4 extend the model in SC 1–SC 2 to include constraints (3), modelling the dependence of gas consumption of households on electricity for both the reference and the congested cases, in that order. To do that, we assume that all electric loads in zones 11, 21, and 31 belong to households. As similarly done in SC 1–SC 2, we assume a 70% reduction of gas production.
- Scenario 5 (SC 5): This scenario analyses the effect of fuel-switching capabilities in the identification of critical GFPPs. We impose fuel-switching capabilities to the GFPPs located at bus 213. In this scenario, the model is (1)–(4). We assume that the backup fuel is light oil, its price is 30.5 \$/MWh, and the maximum backup fuel offtake per hour is set to 1.5 GWh. This maximum limit does not impose any constraint in the formulation since the fuel offtake for the GFPPs located at bus 213 when working at full capacity is equal to 1.1 GWh per hour. Four different cases are then analysed:
- Case 5.a: Reference case, $k = 1$, and 73.3 GWh of maximum backup fuel offtake per week.
 - Case 5.b: Reference case, $k = 1$, and 146.5 GWh of maximum backup fuel offtake per week.
 - Case 5.c: Congested case, $k = 1$, and 73.3 GWh of maximum backup fuel offtake per week.
 - Case 5.d: Congested case, $k = 1$, and 146.5 GWh of maximum backup fuel offtake per week.

4 Results and discussion

We build the coupled gas and electricity model in Plexos 8.1. We run a day-ahead optimisation for the week 24-30 August by considering hourly time steps and a 4-hour look-ahead window. The resulting model is run with the solver Xpress-MP 34.01.03 by using an optimality gap equal to 0.1%.

4.1 Scenarios 0-2: Impact of the natural gas network

We analyse two cases: reference (SC 1) and congested (SC 2). Without any gas shortage, the reference case can fulfil both electricity and gas demand. However, the congested case leads to an ENS equal to 11.6 GWh (around 1.3% of the total electricity demand) and dumped energy equal to 0.2% of the total electricity generation due to the constraints imposed by the natural gas network. More specifically, the ENS in zones 11, 21, and 31 is equal to 1.5, 8.2, and 1.8 GWh, respectively.

Table 1 shows the critical GFPPs identified in cases 1.b and 2.b, i.e. when at most one critical GFPP can be identified per time period ($k = 1$). We rank the critical GFPPs based on the number of operating hours that GFPPs have been scheduled on during the optimisation horizon. Note that cases 1.a and 2.a represent the worst-case events in which no GFPP would be operational, thus no identification of critical GFPPs takes place for these cases. Cases 1.c and 2.c are less stringent than cases 1.b and 2.b because the set of constraints (4a)–(4b), (4d) to identify critical GFPPs are no longer imposed. In these cases, any GFPP can be used at any time with the goal of minimising the electricity and gas not served while respecting the technical and operational constraints. Hence, these cases would provide per se an optimal ranking and dispatch of critical GFPPs.

Table 1 also includes the results for cases 0.a and 0.b, which correspond to the reference and congested cases when the gas network is neglected. We first compare the results for the reference case (case 0.a versus case 1.b). We can observe that the critical GFPPs shift from the ones at bus 323 to the ones at bus 213. The reason of this change relies on the underlying assumption made in SC 0, in which we assume that the critical GFPPs could make use of the gas without any restriction. In scenarios 1-4, the available gas is constrained by the operational limitations of the gas production facilities. Another reason for such a shift are the technical constraints of the generating units located at those buses. Two 355 MW GFPPs are located at bus 323 with a minimum stable level of 170 MW and a minimum up time of 8 h. In bus 213, there are two 55 MW GFPPs with a minimum stable level of 22 MW and a minimum up time of 2 h, and one 355 MW GFPP with a minimum stable level of 170 MW and a minimum up time equal to 8 h. Clearly, some GFPP units at node 213 are more flexible than those at node 323. Therefore, prioritising the GFPPs at bus 213 would decrease the gas used for electricity production and more gas could be devoted to satisfying the conventional gas demand. In fact, the natural gas offtake for electricity

production is 212.6 GWh for the whole week in case 0.a (98% of the gas is consumed by the GFPPs at bus 323), whereas the gas offtake for electricity production decreases to 146.6 GWh in case 1.b (only 18% is consumed by the GFPPs located at bus 323). This comes at expense of increasing the ENS by 23%. In the congested case (case 0.b versus case 2.b), the top four critical GFPPs are identical in both cases and there are only slight differences in their commitment.

Table 1. Critical GFPPs identified in scenarios 0-4 for both reference and congested cases when $k = 1$.

Case 0.a		Case 0.b		Case 1.b		Case 2.b		Case 3.b		Case 4.b	
Reference		Congested		Reference		Congested		Reference		Congested	
ENS = 75.4 GWh		ENS = 129.7 GWh		ENS = 92.9 GWh GNS = 1.8 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 131.5 GWh GNS = 1.5 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 93.0 GWh GNS = 2.0 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 146.0 GWh GNS = 12.5 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 12.5 GWh	
Ranking	# hours ⁽¹⁾	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours
323	156	107	84	213	126	107	72	213	113	107	65
213	8	213	39	323	24	213	51	323	46	213	56
		323	31			323	23			313	47
		313	14			313	14				
						321	8				

⁽¹⁾ The number of hours refers to the hourly time periods that the gas-fired power plant is scheduled on for the simulation period.

Source: JRC, 2024.

Figure 2. Electricity and gas not served - Reference (SC 1) and congested (SC 2) cases.

Source: JRC, 2024.

Figure 2 (left plot) shows the ENS in each zone of the electricity system for all cases. In this figure, the pink-coloured bars correspond to the distribution zones wherein we have assumed that all residential consumers are located. **Figure 2** (right plot) shows the GNS for all conventional gas consumers. First, we can observe that the total ENS decreases when k increases, i.e. when moving from cases a to c , whereas the GNS for industrial and commercial consumers increases because the gas devoted to electricity production is prioritised. Scenarios 1 and 2 always lead to ENS in zones 11, 21, and 31 where the households are located, whose gas consumption is supplied first. However, this may not be realistic because some households need electricity to operate their appliances, despite the fact that **Figure 2** shows no GNS for those consumers in scenarios 1 and 2.

4.2 Scenarios 3-4: Impact of the reliance of residential gas consumers on electricity

Scenarios 3 and 4 illustrate the impact of including constraints (3) into the problem formulation, i.e. some households cannot consume gas without electricity. **Table 1** reports the critical GFPPs for these scenarios when $k = 1$, whereas **Figure 3** shows the ENS and GNS for scenarios 3 and 4. In the reference case (SC 3), the total ENS and GNS are essentially the same as the ones resulting from scenario 1. Interestingly, there is no residential ENS (neither electricity nor gas) in cases 3.a-3.c. The constraints (3) enforce a new dispatch and commitment solution thanks to the spare transmission capacity in the electricity network. Regarding critical GFPPs, the identified power plants in case 3.b are the same as in case 1.b, as can be seen in **Table 1**.

On the other hand, in the congested case (SC 4), the transmission congestion causes an unavoidable load shedding in the electricity system. In the three cases (4.a-4.c) of **Figure 3**, we can also observe gas shortage in households due to the linkage between the electricity and gas consumers modelled by the constraints (3). As expected, the residential ENS (i.e. the loads located in zones 11, 21, and 31) decreases by 43%, 49% and 57% in cases 4.a-4.c with respect to cases 2.a-2.c, respectively. However, the total ENS increases by 6%, 11%, and 6% in cases 4.a-4.c, respectively. Finally, the critical GFPPs in case 4.b are included in the set of critical GFPPs identified in case 2.b. In order to satisfy the ENS at the zones where residential consumers are located, the GFPPs at buses 321 and 323 are no longer critical in case 4.b, thus increasing the number of operating hours for the other GFPPs.

Figure 3. Electricity and gas not served - Reference (SC 3) and congested (SC 4) cases.

Source: JRC, 2024.

4.3 Scenario 5: Impact of fuel-switching capabilities

The results from cases 5.a-5.b are compared with those obtained in case 3.b in order to analyse the impact of the fuel-switching capabilities in the GFPPs located at bus 213 in the reference case. **Table 2** shows the ENS, GNS, and the residential GNS for each of the cases, along with the ranking of critical GFPPs. In case 3.b, the critical GFPPs are the ones at bus 213 followed by the ones at bus 323. The gas offtake for electricity production amounts to 153.2 GWh and 71.8% of the total gas offtake is supplied to region 2. This solution leads to an ENS equal to 93 GWh and a gas shortage of 2 GWh.

When the GFPPs at bus 213 are equipped with fuel-switching capabilities, the results are substantially different in terms of ENS and criticality. In case 5.a, we can observe that the GFPPs at bus 213 are no longer critical. Note that the formulation may still choose the GFPPs as critical provided that their fuel-switching capabilities are deemed insufficient. Instead, the GFPPs at bus 323 are identified as critical followed by the ones located at buses 221 and 313, in that order. The backup fuel offtake is equal to 73.3 GWh, i.e. GFPPs at bus 213 use their full inventory with the goal of minimising the ENS while satisfying the technical and economic constraints. In this case, the natural gas offtake for electricity production decreases by 10.7% compared to case 3.b (i.e. to 136.9

GWh). In addition, the ENS decreases by 32.3%, but the GNS increases from 2.0 to 12.8 GWh. The reason for this increase in the GNS relies essentially on the change of the critical GFPP which causes 95% of the gas offtake for electricity production being supplied to region 3 (in case 3.b most of the gas goes to region 2). The gas of the production facility at the gas node 3 is mainly used to satisfy the residential gas demand and the demand for electricity production. Since the gas cannot flow from gas nodes 1 and 2 towards gas node 3, the industrial and commercial gas demands are curtailed, thus increasing the gas shortage. From the results, we can infer that having fuel-switching capabilities in the GFPPs at bus 213 may not be the best strategy to minimise the total energy not served of the integrated system because of the increase in the GNS.

Table 2. Critical GFPPs identified in cases 3.b (without fuel-switching capabilities), 5.a and 5.b (both with GFPPs at bus 213 with fuel-switching capabilities) for the reference case.

Case 3.b		Case 5.a		Case 5.b	
ENS = 93.0 GWh GNS = 2.0 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 63.0 GWh GNS = 12.8 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 59.5 GWh GNS = 10.1 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh	
Ranking	# hours ⁽¹⁾	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours
213	113	323	137	323	122
323	46	221	10	107	14
		318	8	221	10
				207	3

⁽¹⁾ The number of hours refers to the hourly time periods that the gas-fired power plant is scheduled on for the simulation period.

Source: JRC, 2024.

Expectedly, the increase of backup fuel inventory in case 5.b allows for a further reduction of the ENS and GNS. Similar to case 5.a, the critical GFPPs are located at bus 323 for most of the analysed period. The backup fuel offtake increases to 125.7 GWh and the gas offtake for electricity production decreases to 121.7 GWh. Although 88% of the total gas offtake is still supplied to region 3, the absolute gas offtake is lower than the one in case 5.a. Hence, the gas shortage decreases by 21.4% compared to case 5.a and the ENS by 5.6%.

Table 3 compares the results from case 5.c-5.d with those of case 4.b, i.e. without fuel-switching capabilities. In the congested case without any backup fuel, the critical GFPP is located in the first region (at bus 107) followed by the GFPPs at bus 213. The natural gas offtake for electricity production amounts to 105.2 GWh and now the gas offtake is not predominant in any of the three regions. As can be seen, the ENS is 146.0 GWh and the GNS (residential only) is equal to 12.5 GWh.

Table 3. Critical GFPPs identified in cases 4.b (without fuel-switching capabilities), 5.c and 5.d (both with GFPPs at bus 213 with fuel-switching capabilities) for the congested case.

Case 4.b		Case 5.c		Case 5.d	
ENS = 146.0 GWh GNS = 12.5 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 12.5 GWh		ENS = 119.0 GWh GNS = 10.7 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 10.7 GWh		ENS = 108.7 GWh GNS = 11.0 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 11.0 GWh	
Ranking	# hours ⁽¹⁾	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours
107	65	107	111	107	105
213	56	313	45	313	42
313	47	207	8	207	12
		307	3	113, 213, 307	3

⁽¹⁾ The number of hours refers to the hourly time periods that the gas-fired power plant is scheduled on for the simulation period.

Source: JRC, 2024.

The critical GFPP is still the one at bus 107 in cases 5.c and 5.d. However, since the GFPPs at bus 213 switch to backup fuel, more GFPPs come into play for a few hours in cases 5.c and 5.d. Although the critical GFPP remains unchanged, fuel-switching capabilities may help reduce the energy not served in the integrated system. Note that the ENS decreases by 19-26% while the residential GNS reduces also by 12-14% in both cases, unlike the situation observed in the reference case.

5 Conclusion

This paper proposes an optimisation model for an integrated natural gas and electricity system to identify and rank critical gas-fired power plants (GFPPs) in order to comply with Regulation (EU) No 2017/1938 on security of gas supply. The electricity system is modelled as a unit commitment and economic dispatch problem whereas the gas system is represented by a mass-flow steady-state model. Additional constraints allow to consider modelling aspects such as the reliance of gas consumers on electricity and fuel-switching capabilities of certain GFPPs.

Several conclusions can be drawn from the case study:

- Congestion in the electricity network plays a crucial role because the power plants identified as critical are not necessarily the ones with the highest installed capacity.
- The consideration of an integrated system may change the degree of criticality of the GFPPs since the gas network may impose additional constraints.
- The reliance of residential gas consumers (households) on electricity does not affect the identification of the main critical GFPPs in this case study, but the ranking of critical GFPPs may be different to help reduce the gas shortage of residential gas customers.
- Adding fuel-switching capabilities to critical GFPPs changes the designation of the critical GFPP and decreases the electricity not served of the power system. However, this may lead to an increase in the gas shortage of the natural gas system. Therefore, it is essential to carefully determine which GFPPs should be equipped with fuel-switching capabilities while accounting for an integrated natural gas and electricity system.

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Disclaimer

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